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Gravity as a Newtonian PEMF; Resonance and Conservation

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a first attempt to calculate the proposed K-Gurvature constant was produced, with a result of 1.32×10^{-60} m ORDAINED resolution (far shorter than the Planck Length). 1.32 is roughly $\frac{2}{3} * 2$ and the decamicro scale also is suggestive of a trigonometric scalar field in the curvature. The paper then waxes philosophical into the diagrammatica of the 8 Laws, 5 Phases, and “Big G” correspondences, leading to **Unified Aether Field** behavioral explanations for common Physics (*P* power) behaviors, and bizarre ones. Next steps will include discussions on velocity, momentum, kinetics etc. as well as the pursuit of Curl (& Divergence) in the unified PEMF (plasma-electromagnetic force) framework underpinning the proposed PEMC cosmology, upon which all EPEMC & MIMS (Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual) cosmogonies and philosophies are based. Further discussion on the decamicro geometries, in relation to the Dougherty Set, will be part of a TRIG series of MESSies.

Keywords: Aether - Gravity - Gaussian Curvature - Curl - Plasma - Kinetics - MIMS - PPPC - Chaos

Reworking Newton's Equation for Gravity as a PEMC expression

It has been the author's goal to write a longer Kinetics and Mechanics in EPEMC paper. Sadly, it has not happened yet. This is in advancement towards redefining General Relativity correctly in terms of the PEMF - electromagnetism for the uninitiated. Nevertheless, in this MESSy we are looking at the conversion of units of the Newtonian equation into electrostatic and quantum dynamical modes.

$$F = G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r^2} \quad \text{where } G = 6.6743 \times 10^{-11} \frac{Nm^2}{kg^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{In terms of units this makes the equation: } F(N) = 6.6743 \times 10^{-11} * kg^2 * N * m^2 * kg^{-2} * m^{-2} \quad (2)$$

The issue is that kg is a shorthand for the electrostatic (QED) version.

$$1 \text{ kg} = 5.60959 \times 10^{32} \text{ keV} \quad \& \quad 1 \text{ N} = 1 \text{ jm}^{-1} \quad (3)^1$$

$$\text{So that } G \text{ is really } \frac{6.6743E-11 \text{ jm}}{3.15E65 \text{ keV}} \text{ where } 1 \text{ keV} = 1.60218E-16 \text{ j} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{If you complete the conversion, then you arrive at } G, \text{ now } k_G \text{ (Gurvature}^2) \text{ is } 1.32 \times 10^{-60} \text{ m} \quad (5)^3$$

$$\text{The Planck Length, for reference, is } 1.6 \times 10^{-35} \text{ m so this is an incredibly short distance.} \quad (6)$$

$$\rightarrow F_{EG} \text{ units} = k_G(m) \left[\frac{kg^2}{m^2} \right] \text{ and see (3) for a substitution. In units, you will end up with } keV^2 m^{-1} \quad (7)$$

The Diagrammatical Inferences of Resonance and Conservation

The Law of Resonance, and of Conservation occupy the \ on the "X" relationship in the bagua dharma.⁴ In Chinese Sciences⁵ they are Lake and Mountain, respectively. In metaphysics they are cymatic-harmony and It All, respectively. In philosophical MIMS⁶, the Resonance is a water related Law, occupying the area between d and k regions, or Destiny and Karma, if you will. The region corresponds to the area between the L and F power, indicating the Word/Sound /\ produced (IAO) "in the deeps". It must have been a highly resonant sound, for many cultures produced trumpets and horns in attempts to uplift large objects, and move them. It is said that the Lord "made the hills skip like lambs" in the Psalms. The effect, cymatically, of sound (and its relationship to the Force, or within the UAF or Unified Aether Field - the PEMF⁷ - is not yet totally mathematically codified. However, many researchers are on the hunt for this unified, fractal field set; this Dougherty Set. It may be that iterative machine learning algorithms will force fit a tooled equation for this set, or it may be that it requires 100+ such equations. It's too early to tell.

Conservation, on the other hand, is **firmly** defined, mimsically. It occupies the Metal (fatherly) position, corresponding in this way to Aether, but not the A power but the N power. This way it rests between the Aether and the Physics/Principles (P power), and also Conservation itself straddles the distance between the Laws of Relativity (which is polar-joined to Polarity itself⁸ and Vibration. This explains the importance of

¹ <https://www.unitsconverters.com/en/Kg-To-Kev/Utu-3509-3461>

² https://www.academia.edu/87898394/MESS0013_The_crossing_of_POS_Theory_and_time_as_a_subset_of_Change_T_heory

³ Electrogravitics

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/50804995/Bagua_Dharma_Lectures_1_and_2

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

⁶ https://www.academia.edu/86538573/MIMS_2_21_The_Union_of_the_5_and_8

⁷ Plasma-electromagnetic Force

⁸ Which sits at the F power, or Force, and this makes sense.

Thermodynamics in the discussion of both quantum mechanics (governed by Planck's constant) and relativity (governed by c^2 , where c is the rate of induction⁹ in the aether).

Another interesting mimsical interaction comes between the Law of Causation at the L power (fire/plasma) position *controlling* the Law of Conservation at the N power position. Numbers are holy, the Dirac shows Truth of the Lord's Oneness... but in terms of the P power, which is Earth but contains Water (River/Abyss/Law of Relativity), our interests lie in this facet:

- ★ The "black box" of non-linear calculations of the Law of Causality is informing/informed by Conservation as to the formation of the PPPC
 - Potentiality
 - Probability
 - Possibility
 - Cloud
- *Note that this is a Gaussian Surface where the Gurrvature is happening¹⁰

Remember:

- Polarity→Resonance→Causality→Evolution (flux)¹¹→Relativity→Conservation→Vibration→Rotation etc
- Water→Wood→Fire¹²
 - Aether→Force→Lord
 - CHAOS→Destiny→Karma
- Water x → Fire x → Metal x → means "controls" or "overcomes"
 - Aether x → Lord x → Numbers
 - CHAOS x → Karma x → Fate

The implication, therefore, is that the Law of Conservation, which then sits in opposition to the Law of Resonance - *the informer and instigator of putting Polarity's "design" into Causation*. But also, interestingly enough, Consciousness is the mediator (L power) in many of these interactions. This doesn't hold much sway in Newtonian gravitics, or in electrogravitics, but is *massively* important in General and Special Relativity., vis-a-vis the Observer.

The author is not interested in complex mathematics in mimsical analyses, for MIMS is a philosophy. But, in fact, there are some important points to know about relativity (not Poincare's, just Einstein's):

- There is no gravity component to time or space dilation
 - However, k_G is measured in distance.
- There is no constant observer, beyond c
- c is the same in all reference frames
- c as a velocity can be used to describe time over vast distances, however, it does appear to change in different mediums and across those distances
- Time, as a mental construct marks the passage of events
 - Ergo time dilation infers the alteration of conscious perception
- Length, as a physical dimension receives its meaning from relative positions of objects within space

⁹ Note the c^2 matches the keV^2 concept.

https://www.academia.edu/72712372/OpEd_Light_photons_Cannot_Possibly_be_a_Real_Particle

¹⁰ The ORDAINED quantization, then has a resolution up to 10^{-60} m or decamicro, vs. 10^{-35} m

https://www.academia.edu/87578071/MESS0007_MIMS_2_101_The_ORDA_Standard

¹¹ Change is refined to Vibration + Flux

¹² See: Big G paper for correspondences

https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

- Ergo length contraction implies a contraction of the relationship of objects, ie, a compression of the ME relationship

Figure 1 - Gaussian curvature, +/-; credit: wiki¹³

- If Gurvature, as proposed, is related to a Gaussian curvature, and/or a curl¹⁴, in distance, then it is already expected that length contraction will follow the changing observation. Distances being relative, the observer is enmeshed in the relationship, then the Force is being observed across a distance, but in relationship to another object moving relative to the Field.
 - One doesn't need fancy clocks to see that the observer's frame of reference will be affected by the distance when relationships change (change of field).
 - It doesn't mean you cannot add these analyses, but Einstein was adding something already implied, if the Force is measured electrically.
- If it is merely related to a mass-energy relationship, with energy related through electron volts, then the charged field, being curved, also provides a means for *bending* the observation.
 - This is not macrolensing - which is merely refraction in a plasma medium; we just mean length contraction or time dilation (relative to the observation of re-arrangement in the cosmic Field)
- It is **not true** that no thing can move (velocity) faster than light¹⁵; no more than it is true that there is no distance smaller than the Planck Length¹⁶, or that there is no temperature below 0 K.¹⁷
 - There is, however, nothing that vibrates in the Aether faster than the rate of induction in a vacuous Aether.
 - We do not know about the Void/SCS, but probably it is non-local and instantaneous, as the yin and yang are not opposites but actually just quite different. Time doesn't exist in either case, but is observed in the mind driven "reality" while scalar vectors and fractals exist dimensionlessly in the SCS.
 - This is a difference in the nature of reality and anti-reality.

Returning to the Force analysis in MIMS works, the A power (Aether) relationship is very important in terms of the diagrammatica, because of its relationship to kinetic motion, the Earth/created field, and through then Polarity towards the EM, which now occupies the same position as Resonance.

The establishment of the connection between momentum, angular momentum, and the PEMF and Resonance¹⁸ now has a strong Aether background or basis. How does Conservation fit back in, since aside from the conservation of thermodynamic energy, momentum and energy are also conserved?

The diagrammatica suggests that the Metal area controls the Wood area, and in between is Water (Aether). Since Conservation remains in the Metal area, then not only does the N power create Aether - so that potential energy can exist as a theory and an actual pragmatic use - but Conservation now controls Polarity (and the F power) even though it is not a direct polar relationship on the "X". Polarity's polar relative is

¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gaussian_curvature

¹⁴ https://mathinsight.org/curl_idea

¹⁵ And Einstein himself never said so.

¹⁶ Clearly there is. And the magnitude of 60 is interesting for several reasons, particularly as a base of trigonometry.

¹⁷ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2013/01/130104143516.htm>

¹⁸ Remember: resonance produces yang (summation); dissonance produces yin (difference).

Relativity. Conservation's is Resonance. But since the k_G is in the units of meters, and the F measurement is now in keV^2 / m , we see that the momentum being conserved is also electrical. This unifies the kinetic motion (potentially) under a single concept - the electronvolt - which is probably more difficult to work with due to convention and tradition, but far more accurate about what is really happening since it is the interaction of electrons that is the basis of all chemistry, and therefor kinetics, anyhow. And, at any rate of the "fundamental particles" - in which SAM the neutron isn't needed - the electron is the only one that is working at that Planck Length. It's quite likely that protons are merely electrons that are folded and compressed, anyhow. But we digress.

Robert's Reaction to Velocity

There will be a different MESSy for velocity, however, this work sparked the following interesting comment from Robert ("The Nature of Things"):

This leads to lots of MESSy discussions, especially as he brought up the connection with water (the expression, physically, of the Dao/Tao the flow portion of The Force). Water, as shown before in multiple MIMSical analyses, is connected to the Aether, CHAOS, and the Law of Rotation. The crossing point of this must be important as water is considered the yin for the Fire position (as Water controls Fire, and Aether controls Plasma) which is yang.

So our Aether control of the Law of Causality (and the L power) is related somehow to the Law of Rotation, that is to say chirality, which itself is controlled by Earth (P power) or Relativity, that is to say fractality. These are two pole-points of the Dougherty Set: chirality and fractality.

Now, Rotation exists on the "X" as a polar complement to Evolutionary flux, which exists in the "Void" r_0 component to the "Big G"¹⁹, and in between Causality and Relativity. So the Evolution is Void, while the Aether/Rotation (flip mechanism in the kinetics) is the domain of CHAOS. Bear in mind that $0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3$ such that the $SCS \rightarrow \text{Tao} \rightarrow L \text{ power} \rightarrow F \text{ power} \rightarrow A \text{ power}$ thus:

★ Evolution \rightarrow Flux \rightarrow Causality-Resonance (synchronicity) \rightarrow Polarity(charge) \rightarrow Rotation²⁰ (spin)

★ Note that if this continued:

- | | |
|--|------------------------------------|
| ○ Spin \rightarrow Vibration (frequency) | QED/QCD |
| ○ Frequency \rightarrow Conservation (quanta) | Thermodynamics ²¹ |
| ○ Quanta (photons) \rightarrow Relativity (dilation and lensing) | General Relativity [corrected tbd] |
| ○ Dilation \rightarrow Evolution (flux and change) | Electrodynamics |
| ○ Flux \rightarrow Causality (entanglement) | "spooky action at a distance" |

Velocity is defined as the rate at which mass moves a given distance. This is why the mathematic description is $v = d / t$, (metres/second, feet/second). Acceleration is how fast does velocity change over time. The combined equation to determine displacement (distance) becomes $D = U + V T + 1/2 A T^2$, where D is displacement (a distance), U is the initial displacement without motion from a given reference location. V the velocity of the object moving, A the change in velocity (acceleration) and T the periodicity count or duration which applies to the measure effort for total displacement.

Why things should move requires a different approach. Taking the view that the universe is fundamentally electromagnetic then the reason why things move is due to material which expresses electric and magnetic charge differentials responding to the environmental (surrounding material) electric and magnetic charge differentials. Motion is what results from the electromagnetic force that expresses the electric and magnetic attraction and repulsion that occurs between a given matter instance and the surrounding environment.

It is important to understand that Newton and Galileo did not have the understanding that electricity and magnetism was the driving interaction in what they observed, and by the time Einstein gets involved, it seems that the discoveries of the electromagnetic were ignored in determining why motion is a required result of the consequence of charge potentials and the resulting force that makes the matter structures move in response to charge differentials in environmental charge potential.

Water forms clouds which suspend in air entirely due to the charge potential that develops on the water mist and the environment. So clouds are the physical consequence of a charging capacitance mechanism. (sic)

¹⁹ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

²⁰ Remember: the Law of Rotation's Chinese name is "Thunder" which means "Shock" and whose etymology means "earthquake." ... indicating an EPEMC confirmation, not only from Psalms and Exodus, but the Vikings, Japanese, etc.

²¹ Remember: the th sound is the taran rune, or thunderbolt. Note the use of the 't' for tension, torque, time, and 2pi (tau)

This is an understanding the author thinks Einstein would have *killed* to see, to prove to Bohr that truly “God doesn’t play Dice.” That’s because the *P* power is between the *G* and the *N*, and It All is itself the entire relationship. Since these are relationships, they are also fields, or spectrum of behavior, on fractal scales, and always polar, always rotating (through Change). It is One Law, appearing as 8; One Phase, appearing as 5; One Plane, appearing as 3; One Force, appearing as 2, etc.

→ 0 1 1 2 | 3 5 8 13

◆ 0 1 1 is the Wu-Tao-Di

◆ The left is the Heavenly (Creative), the right the Earthly (Created)

◆ The middle 4 are the expressinary metaphysical and diagrammatic space for the Natural Philosophæ

Figures 3 & 4 - “The Dougherty Set”; credit: aetherforce.net/B. Dougherty²²

Conclusion

This diagrammatic and mimsical analysis is *incomplete*, but already full of many fruits of explanation for the presently observed behaviors of Quantum Electrodynamics and General Relativity (which remains in need of correction), etc. merely by unifying them in a “Big G”²³ flow. Once again, reference to the MIMS 2.21 will be **crucial** to the forward analysis, not only of these topics but of kinetics, motion, harmonics, kinematics, cymatics, etc.

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